

AI-PRISM

D3.1 – AI-PRISM Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform (I)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101058589. This document reflects only the author's view and the EU Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Title	AI-Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing
Project Acronym	AI-PRISM
Grant Agreement No	101058589
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-01
Start Date of Project	October 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the deliverable	AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient (I)
Number of the deliverable	D3.1
Related WP number and name	WP3
Related task number and name	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4
Deliverable dissemination level	PU
Deliverable due date	31.03.2024
Deliverable submission date	31.03.2024
Task leader/Main author	IKE
Contributing	FBK, WINGS, TAU

partners	
Reviewer(s)	PIAP, UPV

<p>Keywords</p> <p>Software, versions, Gitlab, AI, CI/CD</p>

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	10.03.2024	Base version	IKE, UPV
v0.2	28.03.2024	Added contribution from partners	IKE, FBK, WINGS, TAU
v0.3	29.03.2024	Reviewed	IKER, UPV

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work Package
T	Task
AI	Artificial intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development/Deployment
2D/3D/6D	Two/three/six Dimensions

The AI-PRISM project

D3.1 AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient (I)

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with **human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable and high-quality European manufacturing industry.**

To do so, we will develop an **integrated and scalable environment** with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. **A human-robot cooperative environment** powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.**

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, **AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes**, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, **25 partners** from **12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

Contents

1. Introduction	8
1.1. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY	8
1.2. STATUS GUIDELINES	8
2. Architecture of the Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform	9
3. Modules	9
3.1. Collaborative Multiagent ROS based Robotic framework (IKE)	9
3.1.1. ROS Framework – RF (IKER)	9
3.1.2. Base Hardware – BH (IKER)	10
3.2. Ambient digitalization for Human-Robot Collaboration (FBK)	11
3.2.1. Ambient sensing infrastructure – AS (FBK)	11
3.2.2. Ambient Digitalization Modules – AD (FBK)	12
3.3. Real-Time communications for sensor and platform integration and control (WINGS)	13
3.3.1. Communications Modules – CM (IKER)	13
3.3.2. Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules – HI (ITI)	14
3.3.3. IIoT Platform – IP (WINGS)	15
3.3.4. Data Platform – DS (WINGS)	15
3.4. Collaborative Simulation Platform (TAU)	16
3.4.1. Simulation Environment – SE (TAU)	16
3.5. CI/CD FRAMEWORK FOR AI-BASED SOLUTIONS – CD (PIAP) ¡Error! Marcador no definido.	
3.5.1. GITLAB TOOLING	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3.5.2. FRONTEND TEMPLATE	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3.5.3. CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3.5.4. MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
3.6. AI-BASED PERCEPTION ENHANCING MODULES – PE (FBK) ¡Error! Marcador no definido.	
3.6.1. OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION (2D/3D) ¡Error! Marcador no definido.	
3.6.2. OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION	¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.7. AI-BASED AGENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – DR (KUL) ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.7.1. COORDINATION OF AGENTS ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.8. AI-BASED AMBIENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – CR (UPV) ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.8.1. REASONING MODEL..... ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.8.2. SCHEDULING MODULE ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.9. HUMAN - MACHINE INTERACTION (HMI) MODULES – HI (KUL)¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.9.1. KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE.. ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.10. PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT – PD (KUL)¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.10.1. DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

3.10.2. EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT..... ¡Error! Marcador no definido.

4. Conclusions..... 17

4.1.1. SUMMARY 17

4.1.2. NEXT STEPS 17

1. Introduction

1.1. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

Deliverable describes consecutive releases of the AI-PRISM software which includes libraries for real time communication, ambient digitalization, and simulation. This includes code repositories, and pipelines to support the development of new modules, their deployment and testing. The simulation platform supports specific developed modules for agent simulation and for collaboration and risks evaluation.

The following specific objectives are targeted in WP3:

- Design and validation of a robotic framework based on ROS for the integration of the technological modules.

- A digitalization module able to map the environment from pre-existing data-models and different sensors in the environment.
- Design a unified AI-PRISM Data Model will be developed describing data flows, offering access to topics and data management functions.
- Develop a new simulation platform that will enable the simulation of specific production plants or lines. including the interaction between existing agents will be developed.

STATUS GUIDELINES

Status	Description
Planned	Task defined and assigned to an Epic
In progress	Task under current development
Ready to test	Task developed and ready to be tested
Completed	Task finished and tested
On hold	Task temporary paused

2. Architecture of the Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform

All modules below are developed as part of WP3 – Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform.

Repository is available:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3>

3. Modules

3.1. Collaborative Multiagent ROS based Robotic framework (IKE)

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework>

3.1.1. ROS Framework – RF (IKER)

Module name		ROS Framework		
General description		The ROS Framework acts as a nexus between all the different devices and modules required to command a robot. Ranging from the controller that gathers data, to the controller that conducts the robot, including any module involved in the tasks in between, them being, data treatment, path planning, IA algorithms, etc...		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/ros2_base		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	It includes the docker-compose files to deploy said image as well as a network to allow other modules to easily connect to it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compatible with amd_x64 devices • Added deployment documentation. 	Completed
3.0	TBD	It includes the docker-compose files to deploy the non-development image.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compatible with arm_x64 devices 	In progress

3.1.2. Base Hardware – BH (IKER)

Module name		Base Hardware
General description		Interfaces to control base hardware. Other modules will use these interfaces to manage and interact with hardware devices

Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Documentation regarding Oculus Touch support for ubuntu systems added. Sawyer robot image added by combining a ROS1 image, a ROS2 image and ROS-bridge. RealSense image added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oculus Touch documentation • ROS2 support for sawyer robot and Docker-compose file to deploy it • ROS2 support for RealSense sensor and Docker-compose file to deploy it 	Completed
3.0	TBD		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for more drivers 	In progress

3.2. **Ambient digitalization for Human-Robot Collaboration (FBK)**

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ambient-digitalization>

3.2.1. **Ambient sensing infrastructure – AS (FBK)**

Module name	Ambient sensing infrastructure
General description	Interfaces to control sensing infrastructure equipment. Communication modules will manage and exchange information with sensing hardware devices using these interfaces

Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ambient-digitalization/ambient-sensing-infrastructure		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Drivers containerized providing compatibility with ROS2, for the RealSense and the UAM05LP sensors. A tool to intrinsically calibrate generic cameras has also been provided.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RealSense driver added • UAM05LP driver added • Intrinsic camera calibration tool 	Completed
3.0	TBD	ROS2 compatible tool to determine the position of a camera when a reference is placed in front of it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extrinsic calibration tool 	In progress

3.2.2. Ambient Digitalization Modules – AD (FBK)

Module name	Ambient Digitalization Modules			
General description	Interfaces to integrate ambient digitalization modules into the ROS framework			
Gitlab link				
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	TBD	ROS implementations of the digitalization tools for each of the use case pilots.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIGO digitalization • SIL hood digitalization • AW chairs digitalization 	In progress
3.0	March 31 st 2024			

3.3. Real-Time communications for sensor and platform integration and control (WINGS)

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications>

3.3.1. Communications Modules – CM (IKER)

Module name		Communications Modules		
General description		Device Management interfaces to manage robots and ambient sensing infrastructure devices in the ambient from AI-PRISM. The IIoT Platform will use these interfaces to manage devices and communications with higher layers in a centralized way		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/communications_modules		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed

2.0	March 31 st 2024	This module captures any message streamed through a ROS2 topic starting with /mqtt/ and streams it through an MQTT topic to the IIoT platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT bridge image added 	Completed
3.0	TBD	Add dynamic support for other kinds of messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic support for non-predefined messages. 	In progress

3.3.2. Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules – HI (ITI)

Module name	Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules			
General description	Interfaces to manage and control communications network equipment. The IIoT Platform will use these (northbound) interfaces of real time communications infrastructure to manage QoS in the network.			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/real-time-communications-network-modules			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This module connects a software-defined wireless sensor network and an orchestration system. The wireless sensor network gathers data and shares it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SD-IWSN Southbound • MQTT bridge 	Completed

		through a set of MQTT brokers.		
3.0	TBD	First release of the SDN controller, integrated with orchestration capabilities for wireless devices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDN Controller • Resource allocation • Northbound API 	In progress

3.3.3. IIoT Platform – IP (WINGS)

Module name	IIoT Platform			
General description	Interfaces to Control equipment from higher-level reasoning modules. Higher-level reasoning modules will use these interfaces to define or update scheduled tasks, control rules or constraints			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/iiot-platform_ip_wings			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	TBD	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	In progress
2.0				
3.0				

3.3.4. Data Platform – DS (WINGS)

Module name	Data Platform
General description	The Data Platform provides centralised batch and streaming services to access data through these interfaces
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/data-platform

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Added video streaming module that gathers any topic streaming images and publishes it into the MQTT server.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WINGSChariot 	Completed
3.0				

3.4. Collaborative Simulation Platform (TAU)

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.4-collaborative-simulation-platform>

3.4.1. Simulation Environment – SE (TAU)

Module name	Simulation Environment
General description	Tool that allows photorealistic 3D representations of a collaborative manufacture environment, including robots, industrial equipment, and human agents. It will help industrial partners to simulate processes in a more realistic way, considering human operators in the simulation. With the SE, users will be able to recreate production plants and lines, taking into consideration interactions between the existing agents in the environment and integrating human avatars.
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.4-collaborative-simulation-platform/simulation-environment_se_tau
Released versions	

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	31 st March 2024	First release of the database structure (SQLite) of the Simulation Environment and the front-end of the HRPI (Human-Robot Physical Interaction) module based on Nvidia Omniverse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database creation • Front-end of the HRPI module based provided mock-ups 	Completed
3.0	TBD	First release of the back-end of the HRPI module with its functionalities to calculate the level of interaction between agents. First integration of photo-realistic digital human workers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Back-end of HRPI module • Photo-realistic digital human workers 	In progress

4. Conclusions

4.1.1. SUMMARY

The report describes the software versions and their status in a tabular manner.

4.1.2. NEXT STEPS

The next versions of deliverable will contain descriptions of subsequent versions of the software and new ones if they have not been created yet.